

INFLUENCE OF EVENING PHYSICAL ACTIVITIES ON SELECTED PHYSICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL VARIABLES AMONG ENGINEERING COLLEGE STUDENTS

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Abstract:

Objective: The current study aimed to examine the influence of evening physical activities on selected physical and physiological variables among engineering college students.

Methodology: To achieve the purpose of the study, 30 male engineering college students were selected from MEPCO Schlenk Engineering College, Amathur and considered as subjects. The students ages ranged between 18 and 25 years. The selected students were randomly assigned into two groups: Evening Physical Activity Group (EPAG) (n=15), and Control Group (CG) (n=15). The study was restricted to selected dependent variables, including physical variables (Hamstring flexibility and Shoulder strength) and psychological variables (Self-confidence and Achievement motivation). The independent variable was the evening sessions of physical activities. The EPAG underwent evening physical activities, and the CG did not undergo any training, except for their routine work. The respective training group was given 3 days of training per week for a period of twelve weeks. Data collected from the two groups before and after the training period were statistically examined for significant improvement using the dependent t' test. In all cases, a 0.05 level of significance was fixed for the tests.

Results: The results indicated that the physical and psychological variables namely Hamstring flexibility, Shoulder strength, Self-confidence, and Achievement motivation, significantly over the changes due to the evening physical activities.

Conclusion: The evening physical activities were feasible and effective training programs to achieve an optimum level of selected physical variables (Hamstring flexibility and Shoulder strength) and psychological variables (Self-confidence and Achievement motivation) in engineering college students over a 12-week training period.

Key Words: Physical Activity, Hamstring Flexibility, Shoulder Strength, Self-Confidence, Achievement Motivation and Engineering College Students.

Introduction:

Evening physical activity refers to any form of exercise or movement that occurs during the latter part of the day, typically after late afternoon and before bedtime. Engaging in physical activity during this time can encompass various activities such as walking, jogging, yoga, or strength training. These activities aim to promote fitness, improve cardiovascular health, enhance flexibility, and boost overall well-being. Evening physical activity is often chosen for its convenience, allowing individuals to unwind after a day's work while reaping the benefits of exercise. It can also aid in relaxation and stress reduction, making it a popular choice for those seeking to maintain a healthy lifestyle.

Methodology:

To achieve the purpose of the study, 30 male engineering college students were selected from MEPCO Schlenk Engineering College, Amathur, and considered as subjects. The students ages ranged between 18 and 25 years. The selected students were randomly assigned into two groups: Evening Physical Activity Group (EPAG) (n=15), and Control Group (CG) (n=15). The study was restricted to selected dependent variables, including physical variables (Hamstring flexibility and Shoulder strength) and psychological variables (Self-confidence and Achievement motivation).

The independent variable was the evening sessions of physical activities. The EPAG underwent evening physical activities, and the CG did not undergo any training, except for their routine work. The respective training group was given 3 days of training per week for a period of twelve weeks. Data collected from the two groups before and after the training period were statistically examined for significant improvement using the dependent t' test. In all cases, a 0.05 level of significance was fixed for the tests.

Criterion Measures: It is evaluate selected physical and psychological variables where chosen as the criterion measures to this study for testing.

Table 1: Criterion Measures

S.No	Criterion Variables	Test Items	Unit of Measurements
Physical Variables			
1	Hamstring Flexibility	Trunk Flexion Test	In Centimetres
2	Shoulder Strength	Chin up Test	Number / Seconds
Psychological Variables			
3	Self-Confidence	Illinois self-evaluation Questionnaire (Martents et al 1990)	In Scores
4	Achievement Motivation	Kamlesh's achievement motivation inventory (Dr. M. L. Kamlesh 1993)	In Scores

Table 2: The T- Ratio for Evening Physical Activity Group and Control Group on Physical and Psychological Variables among Engineering College Students

Variable	Groups	Pre Mean	Post Mean	SD	SEM	t
Hamstring Flexibility	Evening Physical Activity Group	111.73	132.33	1.09	0.18	7.49*
	Control Group	110.66	111.63			1.42
Shoulder Strength	Evening Physical Activity Group	12.88	15.01	1.12	0.15	7.79*
	Control Group	12.38	12.55			1.87
Self-Confidence	Evening Physical Activity Group	26.33	31.40	1.19	0.12	11.48*
	Control Groups	21.73	22.67			1.47
Achievement Motivation	Evening Physical Activity Group	21.67	29.47	1.03	0.21	17.89*
	Control Groups	26.60	26.80			0.37

(Significance at 0.05 level of confidence for df of 14 is 2.14)

Mean standard deviation and t-value were calculated for each outcomes measure can be found in Table 2. The result shows that the pre-test mean values of evening physical activity group and control group (111.73 & 110.66) (12.88 & 12.38) (26.33 & 21.73) and (21.67 & 26.60) respectively and the post-test mean values are(132.33 & 111.63) (15.01 & 12.55) (31.40 & 22.67) and (29.47 & 26.80) respectively. The obtained dependent t-test value on Hamstring Flexibility (t=7.49*), Shoulder strength (t=7.79*), Self-confidence (t=11.48*) and Achievement motivation (t=17.89*) of Evening physical activity group. The table value required for significant difference with degrees of freedom 14 at 0.05 level of confidence. The obtained 't' test value of evening physical activity group was greater than the table value of 2.14. The results clearly indicated that the Physical and psychological variables such as hamstring flexibility, Shoulder strength, self-confidence and Achievement motivation of the evening physical activity group improved due to the influence of evening physical activities.

Figure 1: Bar Diagram Shows the Mean Values of Evening Physical Activity Group on Hamstring Flexibility and Shoulder Strength

Figure 2: Bar Diagram Shows the Mean Values of Evening Physical Activity Group on Self-Confidence and Achievement Motivation

Discussion on Findings:

The study found that a 12-week evening physical activities had a significant positive influence on the physical variables namely hamstring flexibility and shoulder strength psychological variables namely self-confidence and achievement motivation. It is also found that the improvement caused by evening physical activity group when compare to the control group. Thus the results are in line with other study of which has, Effects of morning vs. evening combined strength and endurance training on physical performance, sleep and well-being. The results of the study indicate the combined strength and endurance training program performed in the morning and in the evening led to similar improvements in strength and endurance performance. (Küüismaa Schildt, M, 2019).

Conclusions:

The 12 week evening physical activities program showed significant positive influence on physical variables such as hamstring flexibility and shoulder strength, as well as psychological variables like self-confidence and achievement motivation. Evening physical activities resulted in substantial improvements in these metrics for the Evening Physical Activities Group (EPAG) compared to the control group (CG). This underscores that structured physical activities in the evening effectively enhances physical and psychological performance among engineering college students. These finding advocate and physical and psychological benefit among engineering college students.

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